

A Study on Non-Performing Assets (NPA) of Public and Private Sector Banks in Indian

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Abstract

The Indian banking system has undertaken significant transformation succeeding financial sector reforms. It is accepting international best practices with a idea to strengthen the banking sector. Some sensible and provisioning norms have been introduced, and these are forcing banks to recover efficiency and trim down NPAs to advance the financial wellbeing in the banking system. In the circumstantial of these developments, this study endeavors to inspect the state of issue of the Non-performing Assets (NPAs) of the public sector banks and private sector banks in India with special reference to weaker sections. The study is formed on the secondary data retrieved from Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India. The scope of the learning is inadequate to the inquiry of NPAs of the public sector banks and private sector banks NPAs relating to only weaker sections for the period seven (7) years i.e. since 2004-2010. It inspects trend of NPAs in weaker sections in both public sector and private sector banks .The records has been inspected by statistical tools such as Percentages and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR). The learning detected that the public sector banks have reached a greater saturation linked to the private sector banks vis-à-vis the weaker sections.

Keywords: Old private sector banks, new private sector banks, credit risk

Introduction

The preceeding decade has been many positive expansions in the Indian banking sector. The policy makers, which comprise the Reserve of Bank of India (RBI), Ministry of Finance and related government and financial sector regulatory entities, have made several notable efforts to recover guideline in the sector. The sector now connections favourably with banking sectors in the region on metrics like growth, profitability and non-performing assets (NPAs). A few banks have recognized an unpaid track record of revolution, growth and value making. Banking in India was well-defined under section 5(A) as “any company which handles banking, business ” and the purpose of banking business defined under section 5(B), “accepting sums of money from public for the purpose of lending or investing, repayable on demand through cheque /draft or otherwise”. In the process of doing the above-mentioned primary functions, they are also permitted to do other types of business discussed to as

Utility Services for their customers (Banking Regulation Act, 1949). During Bruiser time, three Presidencies' Banks were opened in Bengal (1809), Bombay (1840) besides Madras (1843) with powers to matter Notes. In the year 1921, due to banking crisis during First World War, the three Presidency banks fused to form Imperial Bank of India. In the year 1955, after Independence, Imperial Bank of India was publicly owned and retitled as State Bank of India (SBI) with a primary mandate to go to rural areas by opening at least 400 branches directly.

Banking Scenario

In the year 1957, the seven banks that were earlier assembly to the rulers of different areas or States viz., Patiala, Bikaner, Jaipur, Indore, Saurashtra, Hyderabad, Mysore, Travancore, became subsidiaries of SBI. In 1969 and 1980, Government of India nationalized 14 and 6 major banks respectively. After the merger of New Bank of India with Punjab National Bank during the area of Financial Sector Reforms, the number of PSBs became 27, which are under current study. This is reflected in their market assessment.

While the charge for this change lies mainly with bank managements, an enabling policy and governing framework will also be critical to their success. Comparisons of bank performance established on financial ratios suffer from the problem that financial ratios might overstate performance because of inaccurate reporting of non-performing assets (NPAs) or because NPAs tend to be lower in the initial years in the case of newly recognized banks. Stock prices may, however, capture performance more correctly because markets, including ours, are sensibly efficient in integrating information that may escape financial statements. The means of both unadjusted and adjusted returns for each of the three categories of banks were compared with returns to the Sensex this gave the relative returns for each category. Two important findings ascended. The comparison of stock price performance suggests that, in the insight of the market, PSBs as a category can endure competition from today's private banks. This finding has important inferences for policy. It undermines the proposition that disinvestment, the sheer weakening of government equity in PSBs, cannot possibly contribute to any improvement in performance and that government control must stop altogether. Consequential to disinvestment, PSBs have performed as well as the Sensex and private sector banks. This suggests that listing on the exchanges, a profit orientation, and a quantity of self-sufficiency can together crop improvement in performance and that a transfer of ownership is not a pre-condition for such improvement all these were aimed at generating income or employment to large number of pastoral multitudes comprising weaker sections of society, artisans, and agriculturists and self-employed persons including educated unemployed youth. In India, till the eighties, the banks operated in a protected environment categorized by administered interest rates, high levels of pre-emption in the form of reserve requirements and directed credits.

In the process, plans of certain banks, particularly Public sector banks, are aiming to divide customers into changed segments on the basis of the type of service they would like to condense and also trying to segregate their servicing counters in their respective branches to enable customer to have easy access to a specific transaction. "Electronic Clearing", "Tele-Banking", etc. this paper discovers an empirical method to the analysis of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) of public and private banks in India. The NPAs are considered as an vital parameter to judge the performance and financial health of banks. The level of NPAs is one of the drivers of financial stability and growth of the banking sector.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the position NPA in public and private banks of India
- To analyze the asset wise classification of NPA in public and private banks of India.
- To suggest various measures reducing for NPA management

Methodology

The current study consist only secondary data. The required data have been collected from secondary sources like internet, journals and the records of anxious banks.

Limitation of the Study

This study have certain restrictions, because of time constraints the research has used only secondary data.

Due to non-availability of data, the researches has used only the data relates to the year 2015-2017.

Limited banks have been selected for this study purpose, both from public sector and private sector banks.

NPA and Banks

Non-Performing Asset or NPA, It is called such as though it is an “Asset”, it does not bring considerable income to its owner or is just document. Call it a white elephant if you wish. Mainly, it is having something that SHOULD work but does not. It is supposed to make Non-Performing Assets work. The RBI has issued rules to banks for classification of properties into four categories.

NPA of Public Sector Banks

Due to government policy and privileges, the bankers were forced by the law to lend loans to the needy persons, though they are not possess the required qualifications and full fill the conditions prevailing in banks. Hence this may leads the public sector banks having huge amount of non-performing assets during this life. Table 1.1 presents the current situation of NPA with various public sector banks is presented.

Table 1.1 NPA of Public Sector Banks

Sr. No.	Name of the Bank	Priority Sector NPAs		Of Which, Agriculture		Of Which Small Scale Industries		Of Which, Others		Public Sector NPAs		Non-Priority Sector NPAs		Total NPAs
		Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
	Public Sector Banks	30,848	53.8	8,331	14.5	11,547	20.1	10,991	19.2	524	1.9	25,929	45.3	57,301
	Nationalized Banks	19,908	56.1	5,741	16.2	8,668	24.4	5,499	15.5	280	0.8	15,283	43.1	35,470
1	Allahabad Bank	714	59.4	215	17.6	311	26.4	187	17.3	119	10.8	389	31.9	1,221
2	Andhra Bank	218	44.7	28	5.4	67	13.5	126	25.9	-	-	271	55.3	488
3	Bank of Baroda	1,444	65.8	636	29.0	530	24.1	279	12.7	85	3.9	667	30.4	2,196
4	Bank of India	2,147	47.9	493	11.9	1,360	30.4	297	6.6	18	0.4	2,317	51.7	4,481
5	Bank of Maharashtra	799	63.7	231	19.2	363	30.0	201	16.6	-	-	415	34.3	1,210
6	Canara Bank	1,424	56.8	466	18.4	399	15.7	560	22.7	-	-	1,081	43.2	2,505

7	Central Bank of India	1,633	67.5	421	17.1	932	37.5	315	12.8	8	0.3	792	32.2	2,458
8	Corporation Bank	398	61.1	122	18.7	79	13.1	197	30.3	-	-	256	38.9	655
9	Dena Bank	379	59.0	85	13.0	74	11.5	222	34.6	-	-	263	41.0	642
10	Indian Bank	249	54.2	55	12.0	163	35.5	31	6.7	-	-	210	45.8	459
11	Indian Overseas Ban	1,192	34.6	273	8.0	605	17.6	313	9.0	2	-	2,248	65.3	3,442
12	Oriental Bank of Commerce	911	62.0	275	18.8	383	26.2	250	17.0	-	-	556	38.0	1,466
13	Punjab & Sind Bank	138	67.1	42	20.4	89	41.2	11	5.5	-	-	68	32.9	206
14	Punjab National Bank	2,471	76.9	973	30.4	1,165	36.3	328	10.2	4	0.1	739	23.0	3,214
15	Syndicate Bank	1,098	54.0	176	8.8	238	11.9	675	33.8	12	0.6	902	45.0	2,005
16	UCO Bank	976	58.6	289	17.4	339	20.4	349	20.9	15	0.9	674	40.5	1,665
17	Union Bank of India	1,632	61.3	369	13.9	895	33.6	369	13.8	-	-	1,032	38.7	2,664
18	United Bank of India	897	65.1	204	14.9	283	20.6	400	29.6	-	-	478	34.9	1,376
19	Vijaya Bank	390	39.6	93	9.4	199	19.1	110	11.1	17	1.7	583	58.7	994
20	IDIB Bank Ltd	785	36.9	297	13.9	226	10.4	267	12.6	-	-	1,344	63.1	2,129
	State Bank Group	10,942	50.1	2,589	11.9	2,869	13.1	5,480	25.1	244	1.1		48.8	21,831
21	State Bank of Bikaner & Jaipur	269	43.9	7	1.1	124	20.2	138	22.6	-	-	343	56.1	612
22	State Bank of Huderabad	292	44.9	55	9.4	102	15.8	130	20.7	-	-	356	55.1	646
23	State Bank of India	9,075	50.9	2,322	13.0	2,169	13.2	4,583	25.7	235	1.3	8,529	47.8	17,836
24	State Bank of Indore	210	42.6	19	3.8	57	11.6	134	27.1	-	-	283	57.4	497
25	State Bank of Mysore	295	49.0	43	7.2	123	20.1	129	21.6	3	0.5	304	50.5	595
26	State Bank of Patiala	542	54.0	119	11.8	215	21.1	213	21.1	-	-	463	46.0	1,007
27	State Bank of Travan-core	263	41.1	25	3.8	87	14.6	158	25.7	6	1.0	371	50.9	641

Source: RBI Records

NPA of Private sector banks

Private sector banks came into existence to supplement the performance of Public sector banks and help the needs of the economy improved. As the public sector banks were simply in the hands of the government, banks had no inducement to make profits and improve the financial the Main difference is only that Public follow the RBI Interest rules strictly but Private Banks could have some variations but only after the approval from the RBI! Private sector banks are the banks which measured by the private lenders with the approval from the RBI their interest rates slightly expensive as compared to Public sector banks.

Table 1.2 presents the NPA with private sector banks is India level and percentage of share of each bank holds is also described in the table.

Table: 1.2 NPA of Private Sector Banks

Sr. No.	Name of the Bank	Priority Sector NPAs		Of Which, Agriculture		Of Which Small Scale Industries		Of Which, Others		Public Sector NPAs		Non-Priority Sector NPAs		Total NPAs
		Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt	% to total	Amt
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
	Private Sector Banks	4,893	27.6	2,024	11.6	1,139	6.6	1,630	94	-	-		724	17384
	Old Private Sector Banks	1,613	42.7	260	7.4	475	13.2	869	240	-	-	1,999	553	3612
1	Bank of Rajasthan Ltd.	61	20.9	7	2.5	42	14.4	12	41	-	-	230	791	293
2	Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd	62	41.7	7	4.6	32	21.0	23	155	-	-	87	583	149
3	City Union Bank Ltd	41	44.2	16	17.1	9	9.7	16	173	-	-	52	558	94
4	Dhana-Lakshmi Bank Ltd	35	45.6	4	5.3	6	7.3	26	330	-	-	42	544	78
5	Federal Bank Ltd	443	53.6	65	8.0	18	2.2	356	434	-	-	381	464	821
6	ING Vysya Bank Ltd.	65	20.2	36	16.1	23	10.3	6	28	-	-	159	708	224
7	J & K Bank Ltd	282	61.8	32	7.0	54	11.7	199	432	-	-	173	382	466
8	Karnataka Bank Ltd	323	58.0	51	9.2	182	30.2	101	186	-	-	220	410	558
9	Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	68	28.0	7	2.9	58	22.7	8	34	-	-	169	710	230
10	Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd	59	18.8	10	3.1	15	3.5	33	101	-	-	267	822	321
11	Nainital Bank Ltd	17	70.4	8	34.9	2	9.2	7	294	-	-	6	266	23
12	Ratnakar Bank Ltd	18	62.0	2	8.6	10	35.0	6	218	-	-	10	350	28
13	SBI Commercial and International Bank Ltd	2	62.4	-	-	-	-	2	624	-	-	1	376	3
14	South India Bank Ltd	88	41.7	12	5.7	27	12.9	49	230	-	-	123	583	211
15	Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank Ltd	46	40.2	10	9.0	12	10.6	24	206	-	-	69	598	115
	New Private Sector Banks	3,179	24.1	1,750	12.7	664	4.0	761	50	-	-	10594	769	13772
16	Axis Bank Ltd	525	41.8	248	19.1	140	10.8	141	109	-	-	767	592	1295
17	Development Credit Bank Ltd	60	21.2	14	4.3	52	16.2	3	08	-	-	251	788	319
18	HDFC Bank Ltd	401	22.1	110	6.1	276	15.3	14	08	-	-	1407	779	1807

19	ICICI Bank Ltd	1,940	21.0	1,303	14.1	50	0.5	590	64	-	-	7320	793	9260
20	Industand Bank Ltd	84	33.0	31	12.0	46	18.1	8	30	-	-	171	670	255
21	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	152		40	6.5	101	12.0	2	07	-	-	613	802	765
22	Yes Bank Ltd.									-	-	61	1000	61

Source: RBI

Asset wise classification of NPA

Table- 1.3 Asset wise classification of NPA

Asset Classification	Definition	provision requirements
Standard assets	These are loans which do not have any delinquent are less threat	(a) direct loans to agricultural & SME sectors at 0.25 per cent (b) suburban housing loans beyond Rs. 20 lakh at 1 percent (c) loans to specific sectors, i.e., personal loans (including credit card receivables), loans and advances qualifying as Capital Market Exposures, Commercial Real Estate loans etc., at 2 percent (d) all other advances not included in (a), (b) and (c) above at 0.40 percent
Substandard assets	These are assets which come beneath the group of NPA for a period of less than 12 months	10percent of the total out reputations for substandard assets.
Doubtful assets	There are NPA exceeding 12 months	20%-50% of the secured portion depending on the age of NPA, and 100% of the unsecured portion.
Loss assets	Where loss has been identified by the bank are internal or external inspectors or the RBI examination but the amount has not been written off wholly.	It may be either written off or fully delivery by the bank. The whole asset should be written off.

Table: 1.4 Assets Classification of Public Sector and private Sector Banks

Bank Group	Year	Standard Assets		Sub-Standard Assets		Doubtful Assets		Loss Assets	
		Amt	% age	Amt	% age	Amt	% age	Amt	% age
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Public Sector Banks	2009	22,37,526	97.99	20,613	0.90	21,029	0.92	4,291	0.19
	2010	26,73,524	98.81	28,791	1.05	25,383	0.93	5,750	0.21
Nationalized Banks	2009	15,08,798	98.25	11,086	0.72	13,306	0.87	2,412	0.16
	2010	18,27,061	98.05	18,520	0.99	15,034	0.81	2,841	0.15
SBI Group	2009	7,28,758	97.44	9,517	1.27	7,713	1.03	1,884	0.25
	2010	8,46,473	97.30	10,271	1.18	10,349	1.19	2,909	0.33
Private Sector Banks	2009	5,68,093	97.10	10,592	1.81	5,035	0.86	1,345	0.23
	2010	6,26,472	97.27	8,842	1.37	6,590	1.02	2,166	0.34
Old private Sector Banks	2009	1,27,280	97.64	1,334	1.02	1,327	1.02	411	0.32
	2010	1,52,745	97.69	1,395	0.89	1,637	1.05	580	0.37
New Private Sector Banks	2009	4,40,813	96.94	9,258	2.04	3,708	0.82	934	0.21
	2010	4,73,727	97.13	7,447	1.53	4,953	1.02	1,586	0.33

Source: RBI records

Suggestions

Based on the learning directed, there are some of the ideas given by the customers of how the current banking should be. These are the comment given by them about the development of the banking sector in India

1. Banks should obey the RBI rules and private services as per the norms, which are not being followed by banks. While the customer must be assumed prompt services and the bank officer should not have any anxiety on mind to provide the facilities as per the RBI norms to the units going vile.
2. Banks should rise the rate of saving account
3. Bank must offer loan at the lower interest rate and education credits should be assumed with comfort without much certification. All the banks must provide loans beside share.
4. Fair trade with the customers. More influence from the employee of the bank. The staff should be co-operative, responsive and must be capable of empathetic the problem of customers
5. Internet banking facility must be made accessible in all the banks
6. Quick dealing with enduring customers and speedy transaction without irritating the customers.
7. Each unit of every bank should be high-tech even in rustic areas also
8. Real time gross settlement can play a very significant role
9. More ATM reporting should be provided for the suitability of the customers.
10. No boundary on cash drawings on ATM cards.
11. The bank should carry out new schemes at time-to-time so that more people can be involved. Even some gifts and prizes may be obtainable to the customers for their preservation.
12. 24 hours banking should be comprised so as to facilitate the customers who may not have a free time in the daytime. It will help in fronting the competition more effectively.
13. The variations for saving account opening as high, so they should be condensed.
14. Customers usually complain that full knowledge is not decided to them. Thus the bank should properly reveal the landscapes of the creation and services to the customers. Besides door to door services can also be presented by bank.
15. The need of the customer should correctly be understood so that customer feels fulfilled. The relationship assessment should be maintained.
16. The branch should help cooperation and coordination among employees which help them in well-organized working.
17. Maintenance of proper grading should be done. A good grading set up can ensure better results within the bank.

Banking sector is cultivating by leaps but still it needs to be enhanced. Proper and efficient relationship staffs having knowledge for one stop banking, customer friendly atmosphere, and better rate of interest are need of the hour. The concept of transfer has overall improved the facilities in all the banks. Household banking will be order of the day.

Conclusion

It is right time to take suitable and stringent measures to get rid of NPA problem. An efficient management information system should be developed. The bank staff involved in sanctioning the advances should be trained about the proper documentation and charge of securities and motivated to take measures in preventing advances turning into NPA. Public banks must pay attention on their functioning to complete private banks. Banks should be well versed in proper selection of browser/project and in analyzing the financial statement

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